

Study of Transition Metal Complexes of Vanillin-Anthranilate

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Manuscript received 23 February 1983, revised 10 April 1984, accepted 8 November 1984

Complexation behaviour of vanillin-anthranilate (Van-An) towards Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , and Fe^{III} has been studied. The resulting complexes are characterised on the basis of analytical, infrared and electronic spectral, and magnetic susceptibility data. The Schiff base coordinates through O and N atoms acting as a bidentate monobasic ligand. The subnormal magnetic moments obtained (at room temperature) in case of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes have been indicated due to oxygen bridged dimeric structure in the light of ir spectral data.

METAL complexes of various Schiff bases have been studied¹⁻³. The Schiff bases derived from amino acids are known to play important role in biological reactions⁴. The Schiff bases containing more than one chromophoric groups and/or extended conjugated systems are most important. The metal complexes of these Schiff bases exhibit unusual magnetic and structural properties^{5,6}. In continuation of our studies on transition metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from vanillin^{7,8}, it was thought quite fruitful to study the avidity of vanillin-anthranilate (Van-An) for the transition metal ions, which are present in the body in traces and are associated with the various enzyme systems. This paper reports the results of our studies on the synthesis and characterisation of Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes of vanillin-anthranilate (Van-An).

Experimental

All the reagents used were A.R. (B.D.H.) or G.R. (S.M.) chemicals.

Preparation of Schiff base: On mixing the alcoholic solutions of vanillin and anthranilic acid in 1 : 1 molar ratio, a yellow solution was obtained, which on concentration (by evaporation or distillation of excess of the solvent) and subsequent addition of excess of water gave the orange-yellow Schiff base, $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7(\text{OH})(\text{OCH}_3)\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COOH}$. The Schiff base was purified by recrystallising it from ethanol, m.p. 290°, soluble in alkali, alcohol and dioxan.

Preparation of complexes: Metal complexes of Van-An were prepared by refluxing aqueous solutions of the metal salt and sodium salt of the Schiff base in 1 : 2 molar ratio for 2-3 h. The metal salts used were $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Sodium salt of the Schiff base was prepared by dissolving Van-An in just required quantity of a dilute solution of NaOH. The insoluble complexes separated out on cooling were filtered, washed with water and alcohol, dried in vacuum and were analysed for percentage of the metal, C, H and N microanalytically.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out using the Gouy method at the room temperature (24°). Diamagnetic corrections were estimated from Pascal's constants. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 337 infrared spectrophotometer and the electronic spectra were obtained on Beckman 26 spectrophotometer. The data of the study are recorded in Tables 1-3.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) and conductometric study reveal the molecular formula of the isolated metal complexes of Van-An as $\text{ML}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Non-formation of 1 : 3 complex may probably be

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF VAN-AN COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} at 24° B.M.
		Metal	C	H	N	
Fe(Van-An) ₂ (OH).H ₂ O	Brown	8.87 (8.84)	56.68 (56.97)	4.41 (4.43)	4.40 (4.43)	2.00
Mn(Van-An) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow	8.74 (8.70)	57.30 (57.06)	4.47 (4.44)	4.9 (4.44)	1.50
Co(Van-An) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Light pink	9.32 (9.28)	56.78 (56.67)	4.46 (4.40)	4.37 (4.40)	1.50
Ni(Van-An) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Light green	9.31 (9.25)	56.95 (56.72)	4.35 (4.41)	4.46 (4.41)	2.50
Cu(Van-An) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Green	9.98 (9.93)	56.41 (56.29)	4.41 (4.38)	4.36 (4.38)	2.20

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF VAN-AN AND ITS COMPLEXES

Van-An	Bands in uv spectra (kK)					Assignments	
	Iron*		Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}		Mn
	II	III					
37.9	42.5	41.7	45.4 41.7	45.4	43.5	—	$\pi-\pi^*$ Aromatic ring
33.5	34.5	35.7	35.7	35.7	35.1	35.7	$\pi-\pi^*$ Whole aromatic molecule <i>trans</i>
28.6	—	—	—	—	—	—	C.T.
Bands in visible spectra (kK)							
Ni ^{II}		27.0		³ A _{2g} (F)→ ³ T _{1g} (F)			Octahedral
Mn ^{II}		27.0		⁴ T _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g}			Octahedral
		30.3		² T _{2g} → ² E _g			Octahedral

*II Complex isolated with the Fe^{II} salt, III The complex isolated with the Fe^{III} salt.

TABLE 3—BANDS IN IR SPECTRA (cm⁻¹) OF VAN-AN AND ITS COMPLEXES

Van-An sodium salt	Iron*		Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Mn ^{II}	Assignments
	II	III					
3630 s	3500	3600 vs	3680 –	3660 –	3660 –	3660 –	ν (OH)
	3400	3640 – 3500 b, s	3360 bs	3350 bs	3360 bs	3350 bs	
1700 vs							
1690 vs	1610 vs	1615 vs	1610 vs	1610 vs	1610 vs	1615 vs	ν Active – (CH=N)–
1630 vs							
1575	1590 vs	1580 vs	1580 vs	1595 vs	1590 vs	1590 vs	ν asym. (OCO)
1418	1325 m	1340 vs	1325 vs	1325 vs	1325 s	1320 s	ν sym. (OCO)
157	287	275	285	285	235	290	$\Delta\nu$
1270 vs	1270 vs	1265 vs	1270 s	1270 m	1270 m	1270 m	ν (C – O)
1030 vs	1025 m	1030 m	1035 vs	1040 vs	1040 s	1030 s	Methoxy group
	810 w	810 w	810 vs	810 vs	810 s	810 s	Coord. H ₂ O
	570 m	565 m	565 w	570 m	570 w	570 w	ν (M – N)
	475 s	480 s	480 w	475 w	475 w	480 s	ν (M – O)
			1085 m	1095 m		1080 m	ν dimer

*Explanations as in Table 2.

due to the steric effect of the bulky ligand molecule. These complexes were found to be nonfusible upto 300° and insoluble in water and common organic solvents.

Magnetic susceptibility: The μ_{eff} values of the complexes obtained at room temperature 24°, in

general, show them to be low-spin octahedral complexes. However, the subnormal values of magnetic moments in case of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes indicate a dimeric structure in the solid state.

The magnetic moment value (1.93 B.M.) obtained for Fe^{II}-Van-An complex is quite abnormal,

since it is higher than the value for single unpaired electron but very much less than the expected value of 4.9-5.7 B.M. for a high-spin octahedral or tetrahedral Fe^{II} complex. The low-spin octahedral complexes of Fe^{II} are diamagnetic while the low-spin Fe^{II} complexes in tetrahedral geometry are rare and have two unpaired electrons, with μ_{eff} values in the range 2.9 to 3.3 B.M. Thus, the μ_{eff} value obtained for Fe^{II} complex in this study indicates either oxidation of Fe^{II} to Fe^{III} by transfer of an electron from metal to the ligand and accounting for the presence of single electron, with the low-spin octahedral stereochemistry or shows formation of the rare low-spin tetrahedral complex of Fe^{II} giving a subnormal value of magnetic moment and indicating its polymeric nature. The spectral studies, discussed later, confirms the first possibility, that Fe^{II} ion is oxidised to Fe^{III} during isolation of the complex and is present in an octahedral environment. Thus, the observed value of μ_{eff} (1.93 B.M.) for the isolated complex is accounted for the Fe^{III}-Van-An in a low-spin octahedral stereochemistry. The value of μ_{eff} obtained for the Fe^{III}-Van-An complex (2.0 B.M.) is identical with this value, showing that both the complexes have Fe^{III} in an octahedral environment with the low-spin state^{9,10}.

The magnetic moment values obtained for Co^{II} (1.5), Ni^{II} (2.5) and Mn (1.5 B.M.) complexes in this study are much lower than the expected values for the high-spin octahedral complexes of these metal ions and show their polymeric nature in the solid state. Thus, the μ_{eff} value obtained for Ni^{II}-Van-An is 2.5 B.M., which is much less than the values expected for a high-spin octahedral^{11,12} and tetrahedral¹³ Ni^{II} complexes. This low value may either be due to the distortion of the symmetry or due to the polymeric nature of the complex in the solid state. The electronic spectra, discussed later, shows only octahedral stereochemistry of the Ni^{II}-Van-An complex, thus indicating the dimeric nature of the complex, as suggested in other cases^{14,15}. Similarly, much lower values of μ_{eff} for Co^{II}-Van-An (1.5) and Mn^{II}-Van-An (1.5) than the spin-only value (1.7 B.M.) expected in the low-spin octahedral complexes of these ions suggest the presence of metal-metal antiferromagnetic interaction resulting in the dimeric structures 3. For the Cu^{II} complex the μ_{eff} value (2.2) obtained is higher than the spin only value (1.7 B.M.), indicating greater orbital contribution and distortion of the octahedral structure.

Electronic spectra : Tables 2 and 3 record the uv and visible spectral characteristics of Van-An and its complexes, along with their assignments. Van-An shows three bands in uv region only and gives no band in the visible region. The first band appears at 37.9 kK and corresponds to the perturbed benzene ring (π - π^*) transition¹⁶. The second band appearing at 33.5 kK may be assigned to the whole aromatic molecule oriented *trans* with respect to the double bond^{17,18}. The third band at 28.6 kK corresponds to a charge transfer (n - π^*) transition.

All the three bands are also seen in the spectra of the complexes. However, they show a shift towards higher wavelength in the metal complexes in comparison with the free ligand. It is interesting to note that the direction of the shift observed in these Van-An complexes is just the opposite to that observed in the complexes of Van-Hy (vanillin-hydrazide)⁸ or Van-Sul (vanillin-sulphanilate)¹⁹, and may probably be due to the difference in the site of attachment of these Schiff bases with the metal ions. As indicated by ir spectral data, discussed later, Van-An utilises its carboxylic group along with the azomethine nitrogen for chelation with metal ions, while Van-Hy and Van-Sul have been shown^{18,19} to utilise their phenolic OH group and the methoxy oxygen. Since the electron withdrawing effect of the metal ion is greater than for a single proton, the absorption maxima shifts towards shorter wavelength on chelation of the ligand with metal, with deprotonation, as seen in case of Van-Hy or Van-Sul. But in case of Van-An, probably the base weakening effect of the carbonyl group²⁰, involved in the chelation, results in the reverse direction of the shift. However, it is roughly true in case of Van-An complexes where these absorption bands also move to longer wavelengths as the oxidising power of the metal ion increases. *i.e.* Mn^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II}.

These complexes did not show absorption in the visible region as strong, very high intensity charge transfer band (due to C=O) obscure d-d transitions. However, a band obtained in the spectra of M^{II}-Van-An and Ni^{II}-Van-An at 27.0 kK may be assigned to ²T_{2g}→²T_{1g} and ³A_{2g}→³E_g (P) transitions, respectively for the two metal ions indicating their octahedral stereochemistry^{21,22}. Similarly, the band obtained in Mn^{II}-Van-An at 30.3 kK may be assigned to ²T_{2g}→²E_g transition in the octahedral environment²¹.

Ir spectra : A perusal of Tables 2 and 3 which record the characteristic ir frequencies of the Schiff base and its complexes along with their assignments, clearly indicates that Van-An molecules are attached with the metal ions through the COOH group (with deprotonation) and the azomethine nitrogen atom, forming a six-membered chelate ring (Structure 2). Presence of coordinated water is also indicated in all the complexes.

Ir spectra of Van-An complexes as compared to that of the sodium salt of the ligand show lowering of the frequencies of active azomethine (CH=N) group such as ~1700 to 1600 cm⁻¹. Further, the frequency due to antisymm. OCO is shifted to higher (from 1575 to ~1590 cm⁻¹) and that of ν_{sym} OCO is shifted to lower (from 1418 to ~1330 cm⁻¹) frequency, indicating the coordination of Van-An molecule through these groups²³. The spectra of the complexes show no change in the frequencies for phenolic OH and OCH₃ groups indicating that these groups are not involved in complexation with the metal ion. In complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II}, which have been shown to be dimeric in

solid state by the magnetic study, an additional band appears at 1085, 1095 and 1980 cm^{-1} , respectively indicating N-O link in the dimers²⁴. Similarly, presence of M-O and M-N bands in the complexes are indicated at ~ 480 and ~ 70 cm^{-1} , respectively. The difference between anti-symmetrical and symmetrical COO stretching frequencies in the complexes varies between 275-290 cm^{-1} showing considerable degree of covalent character in M-O bond²⁵. Further, the analysis of the values of ν_{antisym} and ν_{sym} OCO in these compounds clearly indicates that the directions of the shifts in the frequencies due to ν_{antisym} and ν_{sym} are higher and lower, respectively relative to those for ionic carboxylate, e.g. 1578 and 1414 respectively in $\text{Na}(\text{OOC}\cdot\text{CH}_3)$ ²⁶ and 1575 and 1418 respectively in sodium salt of the ligand (Table 3). This shows unidentate binding of the carboxylate group²⁶ in these complexes supporting the proposed structures (2 and 3). A broad band near 3500-3000 cm^{-1} in all the complexes indicates presence of coordinated water molecules along with free NH_2 group²⁷. Presence of coordinated water finds further confirmation in the band at 800 cm^{-1} ^{28,29}.

Structure of complexes: In the light of the above discussion the following general structures for the monomeric (2) and dimeric or polymeric molecules (3) of the complexes may be proposed.

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